

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

ELECTROCATALYTIC SYSTEMS AND WASTEWATER TREATMENT

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Abstract

The synthetic dyes are widely used in dyeing-trimming productions. In most of technological processes the dyed waters appear.

Azo-dyes production is accompanied by appearing of large amount of highly dyed sewage.

Therefore, the searching for methods of sewage purification, which provide high intensity of discoloration and a rather deep destruction of the dye itself, is of great interest.

Physico-chemical chemical methods of sewage discoloration are multivariant, while electrocatalytical discoloration is based on the oxidizing properties of anodic current. Electrocatalytical effect in different combinations results in significant discoloration. In this case, discoloration efficiently depends greatly on the anode corrosive resistance, current density and potential. According to the obtain data, some composite graphite materials can be used in electrocatalytical discoloration of sewage as electrodes-catalysts with high corrosive resistance and activity.

High rate of discoloration achieved for individual dyes as well as for their mixture enable to use electrochemical destruction methods as the basis of technology for purification of sewage, containing large concentration of dyes.

Keywords: formaldehyde, adsorption, catalysis, platinum, chromatography

The experimental data characterizing the heterogeneous catalytic decomposition of H_2O_2 on platinum in solutions containing formaldehyde and saccharide substances are of particular theoretical and practical interest:

Pt/C - H_2O_2 - CH_2O - sucrose I

Pt/C - H_2O_2 - CH_2O - fructose II

Pt/C - H_2O_2 - CH_2O - glucose III

Pt/C - H_2O_2 - CH_2O - sorbitol IV

In theoretical terms, Systems I - IV deserve attention regarding the influence of saccharide substances on the kinetics and selectivity of CH_2O oxidation products in the heterogeneous catalytic decomposition of H_2O_2 . In practical terms, as will be demonstrated below, these systems may be of interest in solving certain environmental problems.

Figure 1 shows volumetric curves characterizing the heterogeneous catalytic decomposition of H_2O_2 on platinum-graphite in a solution containing formaldehyde, as well as in a pure background solution. As seen from the figure, the volumetric curve in the presence of CH_2O is significantly lower than the corresponding curve of the background solution. [1,2].

Meanwhile, the titrimetric measurements indicate a decrease in formaldehyde concentration in the system, reaching 70% of the initial quantity. The decrease in formaldehyde unequivocally indicates its oxidation by the products of heterogeneous catalytic decomposition of hydrogen peroxide. This is consistent with numerous experimental data obtained earlier [1], according to which the catalytic decomposition of H_2O_2 in

CH_2O solutions on platinum initiates the intense oxidation of formaldehyde, forming formic acid as an intermediate product and carbon dioxide as the final product.

Although the ratio between formic acid and carbon dioxide varies within a fairly wide range depending on the conditions, the latter is always detected in the system.

In this regard, the volumetric measurements conducted in the study always involved obtaining not only the total gas evolution curve, which includes oxygen from the non-productive decomposition of H_2O_2 and carbon dioxide as the oxidation product, but also obtaining the curve of oxygen evolution not enriched with gas. For this purpose, the gas evolved during the decomposition of H_2O_2 on platinum in a solution containing formaldehyde was passed through a special trap to capture CO , as shown in Figure 1. As seen in the figure, the volumetric curve of pure oxygen evolution is slightly below the total gas evolution curve. Hence, taking into account the titrimetric data on the decrease in CH_2O , the ratio between the final and intermediate oxidation products was estimated as follows: if segment A characterizes the overall percentage conversion of CH_2O , then segments B and C respectively characterize the percentage conversion of $HCOOH$ and CO_2 . It is noteworthy that the values of the rate constants for the decomposition of H_2O_2 calculated from the background curve (1) and from the curve (3) of oxygen evolution in the presence of CH_2O attract attention. [3]

As indicated in Table 1, the ratio of the rate constant for the decomposition of H_2O_2 in a solution containing formaldehyde ($K_{H_2O_2}^{CH_2O}$) to the rate constant for the decomposition of H_2O_2 in pure background solution

($K_{H_2O_2}$), is less than one. This indicates that the adsorption of CH_2O affects a portion of the centers responsible for the catalytic decomposition of H_2O_2 .

Figure 1.

Volumetric gas evolution curves for the decomposition of H_2O_2 on Pt/C in H_2SO_4 in the presence of sucrose and CH_2O .

Thus, judging by the obtained results, under the considered conditions, the heterogeneous catalytic decomposition of H_2O_2 in solutions containing formaldehyde predominantly causes the oxidation of the latter to formic acid (Table 1).

(Table 1)

The percentage conversion of CH_2O on Pt/C in solutions of 1n H_2SO_4 containing a mixture of formaldehyde with saccharide substances.

R	$C_R/C_{H_2O_2}$	Total percentage conversion of CH_2O	Percentage conversion of CH_2O to $HCOOH$	Percentage conversion of CH_2O to CO_2
CH_2O	1:3	70	60	10
$CH_2O +$ sucrose	1:3	60	51	9
$CH_2O +$ fructose	1:3	55	44	11
$CH_2O +$ glucose	1:3	55	43	12
$CH_2O +$ sorbitol	1:3	58	48	10

Similar measurements were conducted for systems I - IV, which, besides formaldehyde, also contained saccharide substances. From Figure 1, it can be seen that the gas evolution curves for the case where the system contains a mixture of formaldehyde and sucrose (system I) are lower than the corresponding curves for the case where only formaldehyde is present in the system. On the other hand, titrimetric measurements show that the decrease in formaldehyde content over the same period of time remains approximately the same as in the absence of sucrose. Similar results were obtained for systems II, III, and IV. The gas evolution curves in the presence of a mixture of formaldehyde with fructose (system II), glucose (system III), and sorbitol (system IV) are always lower than the corresponding gas evolution curves for pure formaldehyde, and while the overall percentage conversion decreases, this

reduction is relatively small and does not significantly affect the yield of formic acid, while maintaining the output of CO_2 unchanged. [4,5]

The positioning of the volumetric curves for the mixture of formaldehyde with saccharide substances below the corresponding curves for pure formaldehyde indicates additional inhibition of the rate of H_2O_2 decomposition caused by the presence of saccharide substances. To characterize the degree of inhibition, rate constants for the decomposition of H_2O_2 on Pt/C in the presence of a mixture of formaldehyde with saccharide substances (K^R) were calculated and related to the rate constant for the decomposition of pure H_2O_2 ($K_{H_2O_2}$), as well as to the rate constant for the decomposition of H_2O_2 in a solution containing only formaldehyde (K_{CH_2O}). [5]

These calculations were carried out based on the volumetric curves of oxygen evolution obtained after passing the gas through a CO₂ absorber. The results obtained are summarized in Table 2. From the table, it can be seen that the inhibitory effect of saccharide substances on the decomposition of H₂O₂ under conditions where formaldehyde is present in the system depends on the nature of the saccharide substance and increases in the series sucrose - fructose - sorbitol - glucose. As

noted earlier, saccharide substances, when taken individually in quantities comparable to the concentrations in systems I - IV, do not exert a toxic effect on the catalytic decomposition of H₂O₂. The absence of poisoning effects in this case is due to the fact that at the maximum degree of platinum filling with saccharide substances ($\theta=0.5\div 0.6$), the centers responsible for the decomposition of H₂O₂ remain unaffected by the adsorption of the organic component.

Table 2

Rate constants for the decomposition of H₂O₂ on Pt/C in acidic solutions containing a mixture of CH₂O ÷ R

R	K	$\frac{K_R}{K_{H_2O_2}}$	$\frac{K_R}{K_{CH_2O}}$	R	K	$\frac{K_R}{K_{H_2O_2}}$	$\frac{K_R}{K_{CH_2O}}$
H ₂ O ₂	$9,8 \cdot 10^{-4}$	-	-	H ₂ O ₂	$6 \cdot 10^{-4}$	-	-
CH ₂ O	$5,6 \cdot 10^{-4}$	0,6	-	CH ₂ O	$3 \cdot 10^{-4}$	0,5	-
CH ₂ O+ sucrose	$3,8 \cdot 10^{-4}$	0,6	0,7	CH ₂ O+glucose	$1,5 \cdot 10^{-4}$	0,2	0,5
CH ₂ O+fructose	$3,9 \cdot 10^{-4}$	0,4	0,7	CH ₂ O+sorbitol	$2 \cdot 10^{-4}$	0,3	0,7

Therefore, the appearance of the inhibitory effect of saccharide substances on the decomposition of H₂O₂ under conditions where formaldehyde is present in the system may be due to competing adsorption of formaldehyde and saccharide substances. It is possible that under conditions of such competing adsorption, when some of the centers usually occupied by saccharide substances are occupied by formaldehyde, the saccharide substance is directed to the sites responsible for the catalytic decomposition of H₂O₂, thereby predisposing to the inhibitory effects. It is noteworthy that under conditions of additional inhibition of the rate of catalytic decomposition of H₂O₂ caused by the influence of saccharide substances, the percentage conversion of formaldehyde changes little. [4]

The simplest explanation for the absence of poisoning effects of saccharide substances on the oxidation of CH₂O in systems I - IV despite their evident poisoning effect on the catalytic decomposition of H₂O₂ could be the assertion that the oxidizing process is a homogeneous component.

Such an explanation is based on the opinion expressed in the literature regarding the mechanism of processes occurring in the systems: platinum - H₂O₂ - CH₂O. According to this opinion, the mechanism of CH₂O oxidation in the considered system includes two components - homogeneous and heterogeneous catalytic: [6]

The homogeneous component suggests the oxidation of CH₂O directly by peroxide molecules, whereas the heterogeneous catalytic component suggests oxidation by active particles generated during the catalytic decomposition of H₂O₂. Moreover, according to chromatographic analysis data, homogeneous oxidation of

CH₂O proceeds only to formic acid, while heterogeneous catalytic oxidation proceeds to CO₂ with the formation of formic acid as an intermediate product.

Our research conducted on homogeneous systems:
 H₂O₂ - CH₂O
 H₂O₂ - CH₂O - sucrose (I')
 H₂O₂ - CH₂O - fructose (II')

$H_2O_2 - CH_2O - \text{glucose (III')}$

$H_2O_2 - CH_2O - \text{sorbitol (IV')}$

indicates that the presence of saccharide substances does not affect the oxidation of formaldehyde by hydrogen peroxide. This is confirmed by the data presented in Table 3, which show that the percentage conversion of formaldehyde to formic acid when saccharide substances are present in the system remains practically the same as in their absence.

Hence, if it is assumed that the homogeneous component generally determines the oxidative process in systems I - IV, then the negative influence of saccharide substances on the kinetics of catalytic decomposition of H_2O_2 in the absence of such an influence on the percentage conversion of CH_2O in these systems becomes quite understandable. [5]

However, in reality, such an explanation cannot be acceptable because, as can be seen from the comparison

of the data presented in Tables 2 and 3, the percentage conversion of CH_2O , under otherwise equal conditions, is much lower in the case of homogeneous oxidation than in the case of heterogeneous catalytic oxidation. Moreover, considering that in heterogeneous catalytic systems, there are significant losses of H_2O_2 from the outset due to non-productive decomposition, sharply reducing the initial concentration of peroxide, the homogeneous component can be completely disregarded compared to the heterogeneous catalytic one.

Thus, in systems I - IV, the oxidative process is determined by the catalytic decomposition of H_2O_2 , which generates actively oxidizing particles. The negative influence of saccharide substances on the kinetics of H_2O_2 decomposition under conditions of competing adsorption is likely not significant enough to noticeably affect the percentage conversion of CH_2O .

Table 3

Homogeneous oxidation of CH_2O by hydrogen peroxide in acidic solutions.

	$CH_2O+H_2O_2$	$CH_2O+H_2O_2+$ sucrose	$CH_2O+H_2O_2+$ fructose	$CH_2O+H_2O_2+$ glucose	$CH_2O+H_2O_2+$ sorbitol
Total percentage conversion	16	14	15	20	18
Percentage conversion to formic acid	16	14	15	20	18

Generalizations and conclusions

As noted earlier, systems: Pt/C - H_2O_2 - CH_2O - saccharide substances are of both theoretical and practical interest. However, it should be noted that systems: Pt/C - H_2O_2 - saccharide substances themselves are not very suitable for wastewater treatment containing saccharide substances, as according to our data, saccharide substances are weakly oxidized by both hydrogen peroxide itself and the products of its heterogeneous catalytic decomposition.

At the same time, systems: Pt/C - H_2O_2 - CH_2O - saccharide substances can be directly associated with wastewater treatment. As noted earlier, monosaccharides are often intermediate products in the treatment of wastewater containing formaldehyde. There is a method of treatment, which involves adding alkali to the wastewater containing formaldehyde to convert the aldehyde into a saccharide. Air containing ozone is then passed through the resulting solution to decompose the organic components in the water into CO_2 and H_2O , after which an enzyme is added to break down the saccharide into CO_2 and H_2O . In this regard, another option seems feasible, based on the use of the systems we have studied: catalyst - H_2O_2 - CH_2O - saccharide substance. [3]

Thus, wastewater containing a mixture of formaldehyde with saccharides can be treated in the presence of Pt/C - a catalyst for hydrogen peroxide, oxidizing formaldehyde, as well as other organic components, after which the remaining saccharides can be degraded using enzymes. Both methods seem to be equally valid, and it is difficult to say anything about the advantages of one over the other at this point. However, in the

method proposed by us, alkali is not required to convert CH_2O to saccharide, and ozone is not needed for oxidizing organic components.

The system: Pt/C - H_2O_2 - CH_2O - R can also be used in analyzing wastewater from sugar production. Typically, to account for sugar losses in sugar production, samples have to be taken during the production process over several hours, which are then preserved for analysis.

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